

2,7-Dichloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone as an Analytical Reagent for Cobalt(II) and Copper(II)

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A large number of spectrophotometric reagents have been reported for determination of cobalt(II). Thiosemicarbazones have been found to be the most suitable reagents when complexed with metal ions and thiosemicarbazones¹.

The present work concerns the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) and copper(II) by 2,7-dichloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (2,7-dichloro-QAT).

Results and Discussion

2,7-Dichloro-QAT is soluble in dimethylformamide and water. It is sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone and insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexanone.

$1.83 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of 2,7-dichloro-QAT is stable for a week in water-DMF mixture (3 : 2, v/v). The cobalt(II) complex is stable for 48 h and copper(II) for 24 h.

Spectral characteristics of the reagent in DMF-water (3 : 2, v/v) show maximum absorption at 360 nm. Dissociation constants were determined by Job's and mole ratio methods.

In aqueous media the metal complexes are precipitated but they are soluble in DMF-water (20%, v/v) medium. The reactions are quite rapid and require no heating for colour development. The Beer's law is obeyed upto 5 ppm of Co^{II} at 420 nm and 6 ppm of Cu^{II} at 406 nm respectively. The molar absorptivity and Sandell sensitivity for copper(II) are $1.8435 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $0.03 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ while that for cobalt are $0.9640 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.61 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Dissociation constant for the Co and Cu complexes are 7.369×10^{-10} and 3.66×10^{-10} respectively.

For cobalt (2 ppm), the tolerance limits (in μg) for the ions are Ga^{III} 80, Mo 90, Ca^{II} 90; acetate, thiocyanate, oxalate, thiourea, phosphate and fluoride 1000 each. Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II} and citrate do not interfere.

For copper (2.5 ppm), the tolerance limit (μg) for the ions are Ca^{II} 100, Mn^{II} 5, Co^{II} 15, Al^{III} 10, Pb^{II} 5, Sn^{II} 200, Bi^{III} 15, Ni^{II} 5, Fe^{III} 2, Cr^{VI} 15, Mg^{II} 20, U^{VI} 10, V^V 15, Ce^{IV} 50, W^{VI} 200, Ti^{IV} 20, Mo^{VI} 15, EDTA 30, acetate 100, chloride 100, citrate 10, HPO₄²⁻ 50, C₂O₄²⁻ 30. Zn^{II}, tartarate and fluoride do not interfere.

The applicability of the method was tested by satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples. The method is sensitive, simple and rapid as it takes 10 min time.

Experimental

Spectral measurements were done on Carl-Zeiss and Hitachi 330 specol spectrophotometers. An Elico pH meter was used.

2,7-Dichloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (2,7-dichloro-QAT) was synthesised² by refluxing 2,7-dichloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide, m.p. 235–36° (Found : C, 43.82; H, 3.06; N, 18.53%).

A stock solution of cobalt(II) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from cobalt sulphate heptahydrate and standardised³ and that of copper(II) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from copper sulphate. Buffer solutions for Co^{II} (pH 5) and Cu^{II} (pH 6) were prepared from 0.2 M acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate.

Procedure : Test solutions (10 ml) were prepared with Co^{II} and Cu^{II} ions (2.5–5.0 ppm), $1.83 \times 10^{-3} M$ 2,7-dichloro-QAT (1.2 ml), and buffer (1 ml) and diluted to 10 ml with water-dimethylformamide (3 : 2). Absorbance was recorded over the region 350–650 nm against the reagent blank.

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